

Bioceramic scaffolds fabrication: indirect 3D printing combined with ice-templating vs. robocasting

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Abstract

Ice-templating combined with indirect 3D printing is proposed as a promising method for preparation of scaffolds with multiscale porosity, including a well-defined interconnected macro-channel network. Robocasting was used as a comparative technique to produce scaffolds with comparable porosity at the introduced macroporosity and the inter-grain microporosity levels. Porosity, phase composition and mechanical stability were measured and compared for bio-scaffolds prepared by both techniques. Comparable total porosities could only be achieved in robocasting by choosing a significantly lower sintering temperature (950 °C vs. 1200 °C). The compressive strength of robocast scaffolds was significantly greater (6.5 ± 1.19 MPa vs. 2.3 ± 1.00 MPa, respectively). However, the increased level of interconnected multiscale porosity coupled to a finer grain size of ice-templated samples sintered at 1200 °C (~ 500 nm vs. 2.5 μm for robocast parts) could prove to be beneficial for the development of highly porous bioactive scaffolds with enhanced biological performance.

Key words:

ice-templating, robocasting, indirect 3D printing, Whitlockite, hydroxyapatite

1. Introduction

During the last decades there has been a growing interest on using hydroxyapatite (HAP) or beta-tricalciumphosphate (β -TCP) as a bone graft replacements because of their excellent biocompatibility and bioactivity. Biological activity of these bioceramic materials depends on a combination of physical and chemical characteristics that are strongly related to their microstructure [1]. For example, in order to promote the vascularization and diffusion of nutrients necessary for tissue regeneration, bone graft replacements have to be manufactured as highly porous structures (i.e. scaffolds) [1-4]. Scaffold porosity has to be interconnected with a minimum pore size of at least 300 μm for successful bone tissue growth within the whole volume of an implant [5]. However, while porosity plays a crucial role in scaffold functionality, it also lowers its mechanical performance [1, 2, 6].

Additive manufacturing is promising approach to produce porous scaffolds that meet all the requirements in terms of pore size, shape and interconnectivity for bone cell growth, while maintaining the mechanical properties as high as possible. Additive manufacturing, also known as solid freeform fabrication, rapid prototyping or 3D printing, is a general term involving all techniques that enable production of structures via the sequential delivery of energy and/or materials according to a computer-aided design (CAD) [7, 8]. In contrast with conventional porous scaffolds production technologies, Additive manufacturing allows precise control over both macrostructure and microstructure with a high degree of reproducibility and homogeneity [9, 10]. Hence, the mechanical properties of the scaffolds can be tailored by design. Moreover, the straight forward translation from CAD to CAM allows tailoring the scaffolds to meet specific needs of each patient [7, 11].

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4 However, Additive manufacturing techniques also exhibit certain limitations, for example
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6 printing resolution and architectural control are often highly dependent on the selected material
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8 and technique. For example, in the case of nozzle-based systems the resolution, and thus the pre
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10 designed porosity features, is highly dependent on the nozzle diameter [7, 8].
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14 A suitable strategy to overcome these limitations and produce multiscale porosities is to
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16 combine and additive manufacturing technique with a conventional method for fabricating
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18 porous structures [7, 12, 13]. This approach, called indirect rapid prototyping, combines
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20 structures manufactured by additive manufacturing techniques, as a mold or sacrificial template
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22 for the final scaffold, with conventional techniques. The use of additive manufacturing allows
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24 production of scaffolds with a well-defined 3D shape and an interconnected pore network while
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26 the conventional method allows the creation of additional hierarchical porosity in the scaffold [7,
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28 11, 14-16]. In this sense, the combination of widespread, low-cost 3D printing by fused
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30 deposition modeling (FDM) with an ice-templating proposed in this work is good alternative. **It**
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32 **has to be mentioned there that it is not the first time that ice-templating combined with fugitive**
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34 **polymeric template was used. For example Han et al. [17] used polyurethane foam impregnated**
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36 **with alumina suspension which was directionally frozen subsequently, and Reed et al. [18] used**
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38 **3D printed ABS templates to introduce channels into directionally frozen chitosan-alginate**
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40 **scaffolds.**
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48 Ice-templating, also known as freeze casting, is relatively simple, inexpensive, and very
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50 versatile method to fabricate bulk bio-inspired porous scaffolds. Porous ceramic scaffolds, where
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52 the porosity is replica of ice crystals, can be obtained by controlled freezing of ceramic
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54 suspensions, which is followed by sublimation of ice crystals and sintering (densification).
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56 During ice-templating, particles in ceramic suspension are ejected from the moving solidification
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4 front and pile up between growing ice crystals, creating multilayer porous ceramic structures
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6 with well-defined architecture [19]. The idea of using segregation to obtain specific architectures
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8 was firstly pursued by Mahler et al. [20] to obtain fibers from froze silica gels. Processing of
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10 macro porous ceramic structures by freezing and lyofilization was reported by Fukasawa et
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12 al. [21] , Laurie et al. [22] , or Statham et al. [23] and this technique has started to be used more
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14 widely at the beginning of the new millennium. Over the past 15 years, ice-templating has been
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16 widely applied to various classes of materials, in particular ceramics, to produce macroporous
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18 samples, and showed the ability to use a wide variety of nano- to macro-sized powders and
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20 various dispersion liquids (solvents). The composition of suspension, process parameters, and
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22 different additives can change the structure of ice-templated scaffolds as well as the roughness
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24 and density of the inter-lamellar bridges [19, 24, 25].
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31 The aim of this work is to demonstrate the suitability and advantages of combining ice-
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33 templating with indirect rapid prototyping technique (using a sacrificial template) for the
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35 fabrication of bone tissue regeneration scaffolds with multiscale, hierarchical porosity. Porosity,
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37 phase composition and mechanical stability are measured and compared with bioceramic
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39 scaffolds prepared by robocasting with similar macropore size. Among other additive
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41 manufacturing techniques, robocasting was selected because it is well controllable and widely
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43 used technique for scaffold manufacturing with layer wise assembly.
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50 **2. Materials and methods**

51 *2.1. Hydroxyapatite powder*

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53 As a basis of both, ice-templating and robocasting suspensions, commercially available
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55 hydroxyapatite (HAP) powder $\text{Ca}_5(\text{OH})(\text{PO}_4)_3$ having a purity p.a. (for analysis) and the contents
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of main components $\geq 90\%$, from Sigma Aldrich was used. This powder was subsequently calcinated at $800\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 hours in air atmosphere to reduce the carbonates contained in the starting powder. Chemical composition was changed after calcination and further investigated by X-ray diffractometer (XRD).

2.2. Ice-templating suspension composition

Water-based suspension for ice-templating was prepared from calcinated HAP powder with solid loading of 15 vol.% of HAP. Several additives (sugar, dextrin, maltodextrin and starch) were added to the suspensions for improving the mechanical properties of ice-templated scaffolds and controlling the micro roughness of lamellae surfaces. A 3 wt.% of sugar appeared to be the best additive in terms of resulting microstructure of the ice-templated samples and green body mechanical properties, sufficient for manipulation with samples. The final composition of the ice-templating HAP suspension (15 vol.% solid content) is shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Composition of suspension with 15 vol.% of calcinated HAP powder used for ice-templating.

Compound	Weight [g]	Volume [cm^3]	Density [$\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$]	Weight fraction [wt.%]	Volume fraction [vol.%]
HAP powder	30.00	9.74	3.16	34.08	15.10
Polyvinylalcohol	1.10	0.85	1.30	1.25	1.10
Water	51.50	51.50	1.00	58.5	80.70
Dolapix CE64	2.0	1.82	1.10	2.22	2.80
Octanol	0.83	1.00	0.83	0.94	1.00
Sugar	2.60	-	1.59	3.00	-

2.3. Robocasting ink composition

Water-based suspension (ink) for robocasting was prepared from calcinated HAP with a solid loading of 45 vol.%. The calcinated powder was gradually added to an aqueous solution of a dispersant (DarvanC). Then, a 5 wt.% hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (MC) (Methocel F4M; Dow Chemical, USA) water solution was added to the mixture to increase its viscosity. In the last step the ink was flocculated through the addition of polyethylenimine (PEI) water solution (10 wt.%) . After each addition of powder or component, the dispersion was homogenized in planetary centrifugal mixing device (ARE-250, Thinky, Japan) for 7 min at 700 revolutions per minute. The final composition of robocasting ink with 45 vol.% of HAP is shown in Table 2.

Table 2
Composition of an ink with 45 vol.% of HAP used for robocasting.

	HAP powder	Water	Dispersant	MC (5 wt.%)	PEI (10 wt.%)
Weight [g]	53.30	16.10	6.36	2.90	4.70

2.4. Indirect 3D printing + ice-templating

The proposed fabrication process of green HAP scaffolds samples with controlled multiscale porosity, which consists of a mesh 3D printing, ice-templating and freeze-drying stages, is schematically illustrated in Fig. 1. First, a 3D mesh consisting of orthogonal layers of parallel cylindrical bars (diameter, $d = 0.9$ mm), with 3 mm offset between the bars in xy plane, distance between adjacent layers in z direction of $h = 0.66$ mm, and total dimensions of $20.0 \times 20.0 \times 40.0$ mm was designed in 3D CAD software and subsequently printed on a FDM 3D printer (Felix 3.1, FELIX printers, Netherlands). Polylactic acid (PLA) (Silver PLA, Plasty Mladeč) was used as a printing material. Total volume of the 3D mesh was evaluated to be around 4 ml. Printed 3D mesh was **trimmed off**, placed on the bottom of an ice-templating die, and casted by ice-templating HAP suspension.

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4 The optimal initial temperature of the cooling plate, for our ice-templating vessels design, was
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6 set up to $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The temperature of the cooling plate was decreased by $5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ every 20 minutes
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8 down to $-35\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. This cooling rate enables controlled lamellae formation in the whole volume of
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10 the samples with embedded 3D mesh. Samples were kept at $-35\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 hour to ensure complete
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12 freezing and to balance the temperature throughout the samples. The freezing step was followed
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14 by sublimation of ice crystals in a vacuum chamber at a pressure of approximately 10 Pa for
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16 24 hours with a gradual temperature increase up to $30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, this procedure avoids damage of the
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18 lamellar structure of ceramic bodies by ice melting or reaching sugar glass transition
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20 temperature. Therefore, it was necessary to moderate the heat transfer during the freeze-drying
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22 period. After freeze-drying process, cylindrical HAP scaffolds, with controlled lamellar structure
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24 and embedded PLA mesh, with a diameter of 25 mm and a height of 45 mm were obtained.
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60 **Fig. 1.** Schematic illustration of the indirect 3D printing + ice-templating process.
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2.5. Robocasting

The homogenized robocasting ink was filled in a syringe barrel and, after removing any trapped air bubbles, mounted on the robocasting device (A3200, Aerotech/3D inks, USA). The part 3D model was designed in a suitable 3D CAD software (RoboCAD 4.1, 3D inks, USA), and consisted of a mesh of orthogonal layers containing parallel cylindrical adjacent bars ($d = 0.84$ mm). In order to mimic as closely as possible the interconnected pore channel network that would be obtained in the previous procedure upon elimination of the PLA mesh, one bar out of every three was eliminated from the model, leaving a gap roughly equal to d , and the separation between adjacent layers was set to $h = 0.66$ mm. The computer-controlled robotic system was used to fabricate three-dimensional porous scaffolds at room temperature by ink extrusion through a conical polymeric deposition nozzle (EFD, USA) with a tip diameter $d = 0.84$ mm. The nozzle was moved at a printing speed of 20 mm/s following the designed CAD model. Deposition was made in a paraffin oil tank to avoid rapid water evaporation from the ink during printing. The external dimensions of the resulting robocast scaffolds before sintering were 11.4×11.4×12.0 mm.

2.6. Sintering

Sintering of ice-templated samples was performed at 1200 °C for 2h in an air atmosphere. The heating rate was set to 2 °C/min up to 600 °C (30 minutes dwell time), to allow all the additives and separators used during ice-templating and the 3D-printed PLA mesh to be burnt out completely, and 5 °C/min from 600 °C up to sintering temperature. The cooling rate from the sintering temperature was set to 5 °C/min to avoid thermal shock and cracking.

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4 Sintering of robocasted samples was performed under the same conditions as in the case of ice-
5 templated samples, but some samples were sintered at 950 °C, rather than at 1200 °C, for 2h in
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7 an attempt to achieve a similar total porosity in samples fabricated by both methods.
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10 11 *2.7. Characterization*

12 13 *Porosity*

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15 Total porosity was evaluated from measurements of dimensions and weight of the sintered
16 samples. The size distribution of the open pores was measured by a mercury porosimeter
17 PoreMaster (Quantachrome, USA) on sintered samples previously dried under a vacuum. The
18 open pore distribution was used for inner structure comparison between robocasted and ice-
19 templated samples.
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22 23 *X-ray diffraction*

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25 Phase compositions were investigated using a Rigaku X-ray diffractometer (XRD) (Rigaku,
26 Japan). The XRD was operated at a voltage of 40 kV and current of 30 mA, source of X-rays
27 was Cu anode (Cu K α radiation). Results were compared with known data for identification of
28 constituents and present phases. All XRD spectra were taken on powder obtained from crushing
29 the sintered scaffolds.
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32 33 *Scanning electron microscopy*

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35 The microstructure of sintered samples obtained by both methods was analyzed using a scanning
36 electron microscope FIB/SEM Tescan Lyra3 XMH (Tescan, Czech Republic) with digital image
37 capturing system. Images were taken from the surface of fractured samples at low voltage to
38 reveal microstructural characteristics and evaluate grain sizes.
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41 42 *Dilatometry*

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4 Cylindrically shaped samples with the diameter of $d = 6$ mm were prepared from both, calcinated
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6 HAP powder and powder obtained by crushing of ice-templated scaffolds, by uniaxial pressing,
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8 using a semi-automatic hydraulic press BSML 21 (BRIO, Czech Republic). The applied pressure
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10 was set to 35 MPa with a 120 s dwell. To obtain a dilatometric data, the samples were then
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12 sintered in a high-temperature dilatometer (L70/1700, Linseis, Germany) at 1200 °C/2 h. The
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14 heating and cooling rate was set to 10 °C/min. The relative shrinkage curves were converted
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16 to densification curves by methodology described in the literature [26]. After the sintering,
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18 relative densities of the samples were measured using the Archimedes method in accordance
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20 with the EN623-2.
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25 *Compressive strength testing*

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27 Rectangular testing samples with nominal dimensions of 10.5×10.5×10.5 mm were extracted
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29 from sintered ice-templated scaffolds using a precision saw Accutom-50 (Struers, USA).
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31 Robocasted scaffolds were neatened and grinded so that the final dimensions before testing were
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33 11.2×11.2×11.8 mm in the case of samples sintered at 950 °C/2h, and 8.8×8.8×8.2 mm in the
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35 case of samples sintered 1200 °C/2h.
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41 Uniaxial compression tests of sintered both, ice-templated and robocasted samples, were
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43 performed using precision universal test frame AG-IS 10KN (Shimadzu, Japan) at a constant
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45 crosshead speed of 0.6 mm/min. The compressive strength of each scaffold was evaluated as the
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47 maximum stress applied during the test. For both types of scaffolds at least 10 sintered samples
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49 were tested in order to get statistically reliable results.
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54 **3. Results**

55 *Microstructure*

SEM micrographs of robocasted scaffold sintered at 950 °C/2h and indirectly 3D printed and ice-templated scaffold sintered at 1200 °C/2h are shown in Fig. 2. These images show on the one hand the comparable size of introduced macropores, and on the other hand the difference in their shape. The higher magnification insets in Fig. 2 show cross sectional images (perpendicular to the lamellae growth in case of ice-templated sample, Fig. 2b) to reveal the difference in porosity between scaffolds in the tens of microns range.

Fig. 2. SEM micrographs of (a) robocast scaffold sintered at 950 °C/2h and (b) indirectly 3D printed and ice-templated scaffold sintered at 1200 °C/2h.

Porosity

Total porosity measurements were performed on ice-templated scaffolds sintered at 1200 °C/2h and on robocast scaffolds sintered at 950 °C/2h and 1200 °C/2h. Highest total porosity was achieved by indirect 3D printing and ice-templating process (72.6 ± 1.21 %). Total porosity was about 5 % lower (67.5 ± 0.76 %) in the case of robocast samples sintered at 950 °C and about 47 % lower (25.7 ± 2.40 %) in the case of robocast samples sintered at 1200 °C.

Mercury intrusion porosimetry measurements were performed on indirectly 3D printed and ice-templated scaffolds sintered at 1200 °C/2h in air atmosphere and on robocast scaffolds sintered at 950 °C/2h and 1200 °C/2h in air atmosphere to compare the pore size distribution between all scaffolds. Fig. 3 shows the porosimetry measurement results. It is apparent that the total volume of porosity can be divided into three main regions:

- porosity between grains (0.1–5 μm),
- interlamellar porosity (5–100 μm),
- introduced macroporosity (100–1000 μm).

Fig. 3. A comparison of mercury intrusion porosimetry results for scaffolds prepared by robocasting and indirect 3D printing combined with ice-templating.

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4 The main difference between samples fabricated by both methods is the porosity in the 5–
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6 100 μm range, where the interlamellar porosity region created by growing ice crystals during ice-
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8 templating process lays, which is virtually inexistent in the robocast samples, even in those
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10 sintered at 950 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Volume of introduced macropores appears to be lower also in the case of
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12 robocasted samples, but this discrepancy might be caused by inaccurate measurement of
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14 macropores with convex (Fig.2b), rather than typical concave, walls. Intergranular porosity is
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16 also much larger in ice-templated samples sintered at 1200 $^{\circ}\text{C}/2\text{h}$, compared to robocast samples
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18 sintered at the same temperature, but close to that of robocast samples sintered at much lower
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20 temperature (950 $^{\circ}\text{C}/2\text{h}$).
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26 It is again evident in this data that the total porosity of robocast samples sintered at 1200 $^{\circ}\text{C}/2\text{h}$ is
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28 much lower, and that its main mode lays in the region of pre-designed macroporosity. The less
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30 abundant and smaller intergranular pores proof a significantly greater densification in these
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32 samples.
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35 ***Phase composition***

36 XRD analyses were performed on calcinated HAP powder (800 $^{\circ}\text{C}/2\text{h}$), indirectly 3D printed and
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38 ice-templated scaffolds sintered at 1200 $^{\circ}\text{C}/2\text{h}$, and robocast scaffolds sintered at 950 $^{\circ}\text{C}/2\text{h}$ to
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40 compare the phase composition of sintered samples with starting powder. The obtained XRD
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42 patterns are shown in Fig. 4.
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Fig. 4. The XRD patterns of calcinated HAP powder, robocasted scaffold and scaffold prepared by indirect 3D printing + ice-templating and robocasting. Main hydroxyapatite and Whitlockite peaks are identified with indicated symbols

The observed phase composition of calcined starting HAP powder is a mixture of hydroxyapatite and Whitlockite (β -TCP), with the latter being already the primary phase after calcination. The phase composition of robocast samples sintered at 950 °C is almost pure β -TCP, while ice-templated samples sintered at 1200 °C still retains some of the original hydroxyapatite.

Dilatometry

To clarify more the difference in the sintering behavior of robocasted and indirectly 3D printed + ice-templated samples, dilatometric analyses were performed on samples prepared from calcinated HAP powder (800 °C/2h) and a crushed ice-templated scaffold. The obtained results are shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Dilatometric analyses of samples prepared from calcinated HAP powder and ice-templated scaffold. The initial density difference was caused by a particle packing during the ice-templating process, that wasn't overcome by a pressure involved in dilatometric samples preparation. .

The dilatometric analyses revealed that the temperature when densification started is about 100 °C higher for ice-templated samples (~ 970 °C vs. 870 °C) and the absolute (apparent) density after sintering at the same temperature (1200 °C/2h) is about 34 % lower for ice-templated samples (~ 1.98 g·cm⁻³ vs. 2.99 g·cm⁻³).

Compressive strength and porosity

Mechanical performance under uniaxial compressive stresses was evaluated for ice-templated scaffolds sintered at 1200 °C/2h, and for robocast scaffolds sintered at 950 °C/2h, and 1200 °C/2h. The results from the compressive strength measurements obtained are summarized in Fig. 6, together with the total porosity results presented in previous sections.

Fig. 6. A comparison of compressive strengths and porosities of manufactured scaffolds.

As expected, a good inverse correlation is found between total porosity results and compressive strength. The highest compressive strength was achieved in samples fabricated by robocasting and sintered at 1200 °C, whose average value reached 43.5 ± 8.24 MPa. Significantly lower compressive strength values were obtained by both, robocast samples sintered at 950 °C and ice-templated samples sintered at 1200 °C. The average strength values reached 6.5 ± 1.19 MPa and 2.3 ± 1.00 MPa, respectively in those cases.

4. Discussion

Both methods, indirect rapid prototyping combined with ice-templating and robocasting can produce scaffolds with similar porosity in the submicron and hundreds of microns range. However, it is necessary to implement significantly different sintering conditions (950 °C/2h vs. 1200 °C/2h). Furthermore, ice-templating process introduces in the structure a new interlamellar porosity in the tens of microns range (see Figs. 1-2). As a consequence, ice-templated scaffolds total porosity could be much higher than porosity achieved by robocasting using the same

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4 sintering conditions (thus, maintaining the same size of introduced macropores), and even higher
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6 than in the case of robocasted scaffolds sintered at much lower temperature (950 °C), see Fig. 2
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8 and Fig. 6. It has to be mentioned that it is very difficult to obtain scaffolds, manufactured by
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10 both techniques, with the same total porosity (within 1%), porosity distribution, and phase
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12 composition. Hence it is not possible to increase the sintering temperature of ice-templated
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14 scaffolds over 1200 °C, because of the phase transformation from β -TCP to α -TCP. Another
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16 way how to reduce porosity of ice-templated scaffolds would be to increase the solid loading of
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18 initial suspension, but the amount of powder required for sufficient change in total porosity
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20 would lead to a significant change in porosity distribution and sintering behavior (significant
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22 reduction of intergranular porosity, interlamellar distance and enhanced sintering of lamellae).
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28 Regarding the compressive strength, the performance of robocast scaffolds, even those sintered
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30 at 950 °C, is superior to those fabricated by indirect rapid prototyping combined with ice-
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32 templating and sintered at 1200 °C due to the absence of interlamellar pores, and possibly
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34 slightly lower pre-designed macroporosity. Indeed, the flaws responsible for the crack
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36 propagation and precursors of fracture are bigger and more abundant in the ice-templated
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38 scaffolds, reducing the stress required for the initiation of failure in the sample. Although the
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40 intergranular porosity is greater in the robocast scaffolds sintered at 950 °C, this circumstance is
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42 not critical in terms of strength as smaller pores are not likely to be the precursors of fracture.
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44 Despite this apparently unfavorable results, mechanical stability of the ice-templated samples can
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46 be further tailored, and highly porous scaffolds fabricated by ice-templating can be mechanically
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48 more stable compared to competing techniques [24]. However, it would be necessary to evaluate
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50 the potentially negative impact of the expansion of the polymeric template in the ice-templated
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52 structure during the heat treatment, due to the difference of HAP (β -TCP) and PLA thermal
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4 expansion coefficients [27-29]. Another potential drawback of combining indirect rapid
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6 prototyping and ice-templating would be an influence of the polymeric template on the direction
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8 of freezing due to blocking of the freezing front. There is a limit in the volume of polymeric
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10 template introduced in the structure, due to the change of thermal capacity and conductivity of
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12 the mixture (polymeric template/ceramic suspension). Excessive amount of polymeric template
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14 can lead to a difficult control of ice lamellae growth direction (loss of temperature gradient)
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16 during the freezing step. These problems could become significant if total volume of introduced
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18 polymeric template is significantly higher than in the presented example.
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24 Advantages of ice-templating combined with indirect 3D printing are the possibility to achieve
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26 multiscale pore sizes and an increased connection of internal porosity (micro and macro
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28 channels). These are crucial features of bioceramic scaffolds necessary for controlling and
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30 enhancing the biological activity.
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34 The relationship between bioceramic scaffolds porosity, pore size distribution and cell activity is
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36 still not well understood but previous studies have pointed out that a range of mean pore sizes
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38 convenient for cell attachment lies in range 96–150 μm [5, 30, 31], but for successful bone
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40 growth into scaffolds are necessary larger pores (300–800 μm) [5]. These results indicate that
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42 scaffolds with wide range of pore sizes could be beneficial to achieve optimal cell attachment
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44 and facilitating bone regeneration. The wide pore size distribution of indirectly 3D printed and
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46 ice-templated samples (Fig. 3) could be thus optimal. Moreover, the porosity created by ice
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48 crystals fits nicely within the range of optimal pore size for cell attachment, while macroporosity
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50 introduced by the PLA 3D mesh fits in the range allowing easy bone growth in the whole volume
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52 of scaffold.
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4 Moreover it was shown by other authors [32, 33] that micro roughness of bioceramic scaffolds
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6 can considerably stimulate the adhesion, spreading and proliferation of osteoblastic cells. Such
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8 micro roughness is naturally formed during ice-templating on lamellae surface due to the
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10 addition of sugar in starting suspension. Other can be used to further tailor the surface roughness
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12 for particular biomedical applications.
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16 Grain size and phase composition of ice-templated samples revealed to be unexpectedly different
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18 compared to the robocast samples or previous experiences with hydroxyapatite powders [34].
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20 Grain sizes of the robocast and ice-templated samples are demonstrated in Fig. 7.
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40 **Fig. 7.** Microstructure details of the prepared samples after sintering.
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44 Ice-templating process limited the grain growth, and the final grain size is around 500 nm at a
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46 sintering temperature of 1200 °C (Fig. 7c), a size comparable to the grain size in robocast
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48 samples sintered at 950 °C (Fig. 7b) but much smaller than those found in robocast samples
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50 sintered at the same 1200 °C (~2.5 μm, Fig. 7a). Change of the sintering behavior after ice-
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52 templating had already been observed previously for alumina by Zheng et al. [35], but here the
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54 ice-templating seems to affect also the phase transformation of hydroxyapatite to Whitlockite at
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56 elevated temperature, according to the results in Fig. 3. The change of the shrinkage behavior is
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4 related to change of porosity distribution and length of the diffusion path. The dilatometric
5 measurement, shown on Fig. 5, demonstrates that densification of the HAP powder after freezing
6 is shifted to high temperature. This suggests that similar levels of densification are connected
7 with the similar phase transformation, however it is difficult to identify main reason due to
8 complexity of the HAP phase transformation [36].The porosity can influence diffusion process
9 or gas release during the heat treatment, however very high mechanical pressure, in terms of
10 hundreds of MPa [35] caused by expansion of water during freezing can also play a role.
11 Furthermore the difference in the final microstructure at 1200 °C (see Fig. 5) is tremendous
12 compare with relatively small difference in phase composition (see Fig. 4).
13
14 Further research is necessary to fully reveal the impact of mechanical pressure during ice-
15 templating and introduced porosity on grain growth or phase transformation. Anyhow, this study
16 has clearly revealed that ice-templating is a suitable strategy for tailoring of porosity, grain size
17 and even phase compositions in bioceramic scaffolds for bone tissue engineering applications.
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38 **5. Conclusions**

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41 Combination of ice-templating and indirect rapid prototyping has been shown to enable the
42 preparation of bioceramic scaffolds with multiscale porosity, including a well-defined
43 interconnected network of macro channels. The compressive strength of resulting scaffolds
44 seems to be somewhat lower than in the case of robocast samples with a similar total porosity
45 even though in order to achieve a similar (slightly lower) porosity a significantly lower (950 °C
46 vs. 1200 °C) sintering temperature had to be used. However, the increased level of
47 interconnected multiscale porosity coupled to a very fine microstructure in the ice-templated
48 samples sintered at 1200 °C (average grain size about 500 nm) could prove to be beneficial for
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4 the development of highly porous bioactive scaffolds with enhanced biological performance. Ice-
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6 templating also significantly modified the phase composition change during the sintering step,
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8 which could also be beneficial in tailoring scaffolds' biological properties, but further
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10 investigation is necessary to further clarify the origin of this phenomenon.
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Robocasting 950

Indirect 3D printing + ice-templating

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4 **Figure captions**
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6
7 **Fig. 1.** Schematic illustration of the indirect 3D printing + ice-templating process.
8

9 **Fig. 2.** SEM micrographs of (a) robocast scaffold sintered at 950 °C/2h and (b) indirectly 3D printed and
10 ice-templated scaffold sintered at 1200 °C/2h.
11

12 **Fig. 3.** A comparison of mercury intrusion porosimetry results for scaffolds prepared by robocasting and
13 indirect 3D printing combined with ice-templating.
14

15 **Fig. 4.** The XRD patterns of calcinated HAP powder, robocasted scaffold and scaffold prepared by
16 indirect 3D printing + ice-templating and robocasting. Main hydroxyapatite and Whitlockite peaks are
17 identified with indicated symbols
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20 **Fig. 5.** Dilatometric analyses of samples prepared from calcinated HAP powder and ice-templated
21 scaffold. The initial density difference was caused by a particle packing during the ice-templating process,
22 that wasn't overcome by a pressure involved in dilatometric samples preparation.
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24 **Fig. 6.** A comparison of compressive strengths and porosities of manufactured scaffolds.
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26 **Fig. 7.** Microstructure details of the prepared samples after sintering.
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